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Quality assurance

To ensure the quality and correctness of this deliverable, we implied an internal review and validation process. The deliverable was drafted by the work package leader (Jos Vander Sloten, KU Leuven) together with Lise Gheysen. All partners contributed to and reviewed the overall draft. Finally, the semi-final version was submitted to internal reviewers, for a final review and validation.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable presents the developed lecture material in the format of mini-courses per stakeholder group and its test results. Besides, courses that are missing in the current curricula were identified for stakeholder groups in training. For each of these courses, a syllabus was developed with concrete guidelines for frontal lectures as well as practical sessions.

Work Package 7 (WP7) of the In Silico World project spent efforts from month 25 to month 48 of the project in order to develop and test lecture material on in silico trials in medicine for different stakeholder groups. The collected feedback, obtained from the test sessions, is translated into a list of recommendation for future use and optimization of the lecture material. This was a joint effort of mainly partners KUL-MEC and UNIBO.

2. General Overview

- Background
- Development and implementation of lecture material
- Recommendations

3. Background

Currently the workforce specifically trained on in silico trial in the medical field is limited. In order to overcome this hurdle, training of different stakeholder groups is essential. These stakeholder groups have been identified before and can be separated in stakeholders with a technical or non-technical background and stakeholder that are still in training/education (e.g. master or PhD students) or already employees in industry, notified health bodies, in the clinic or in allied medical disciplines (Vander Linden et al., 2023a). Note that technical, in this framework, refers to a strong background in mathematics, computational modeling and/or engineering. The non-technical stakeholders can have various backgrounds, i.e. in medical sciences, pharmaceutical sciences, nursery, etc., but they are all (being) educated in a discipline related to the medical field, while having no or a limited training in mathematics or engineering.

The educational resources developed in the In Silico World project try to familiarize these different stakeholder groups with in silico modeling and in silico trials in medicine. The development of educational resources was taken as a two-step approach. First, a mini-course was composed to allow the participants to get acquainted with some basic aspects of in silico modeling in medicine and get a view on the state-of-the-art research, which is further referred to as phase I. In a second stage, missing courses in the current curricula were identified and syllabi with guidelines for future instructors were developed to encourage institutions to fill the current gaps. This is further referred to as phase II. The developed educational resources and how they should be implemented is discussed below. Afterwards, some suggestions for further expansion the educational resources on in silico modeling in medicine and in silico trials are pointed out.

4. Development and implementation of lecture material

While many topics related to in silico medicine, and in silico trials in particular, are of interest and not much educational resources are readily available, a selection of topics was made by determining intended learning outcomes (ILOs) for the considered participant groups. Starting from these ILOs, the topics of the mini-course (phase I) as well as the missing courses in the current curricula (phase II) were identified.

4.1. Phase I

A mini-course was composed per stakeholder group, each containing three modules on a topic of interest. An overview of the considered topics for each stakeholder group is indicated in table 1.

Table 1: Overview of the topics and the duration for the modules of the developed mini-course for the four identified stakeholder groups.

Module	Topic	Duration full version (min.)	Duration short version (min.)
Technical - training			
1	What is a model?	90	20
	Introduction to in silico medicine	90	25
2	Regulatory aspects	25	25
	VVUQ: hands-on (video + hands-on)	25 + 70	25 + 10
3	Agent-based models	60	25
Technical - retraining			
1	Regulatory aspects	25	25
2	Reliable measurement input	60	24
	VVUQ: hands-on (video + hands-on)	25 + 70	25 + 10
3	Agent-based models	60	25
Non-technical - training			
1	Introduction to in silico medicine	90	40
2	Validation of experiments	85	25
3	Example cases	40	15
Non-technical - retraining			
1	Introduction to in silico medicine	90	40
2	Validation of experiments	85	25
3	Example cases	40	15

In order to optimize the lecture material for the different stakeholder groups, a test version of the mini-courses was developed. With this test version, the stakeholder groups got acquainted with the essential aspects of each module, while limiting the total time. The impact of the test version was assessed in a quantitative and qualitative manner. The quantitative data were collected based on a pre- and post-questionnaire, where the perceived awareness of multiple concepts related to in silico modeling in medicine was assessed as well as the extent to which the participants agreed to statements that expressed the potential benefits of in silico medicine and in silico trials. The qualitative analyses were based on the comparison between the predefined learning goals and the key aspects as identified by the participants. This comparison gives an indication whether the lecture material succeeded in effectively achieving the attempted learning goals.

For an extensive overview of the results of the test version of the lecture material, the reader is referred to corresponding reports (see appendix A1-A4). In brief, the test results indicated that the provided lecture material was able to provide a slight increase in the perceived awareness on the considered topics. A slight, though rather consistent, increase was observed for non-technical stakeholders in training and retraining and for technical stakeholders in retraining. For those stakeholder groups, it is expected that the complete version of the mini-course will further enhance this increase.

For technical stakeholders in training, the increase in awareness was much more dependent on the prior knowledge. Indeed, for topics with a high prior knowledge, a mini-course is not sufficient to provide deeper insights. On contrary, for topics with a limited prior awareness, the test version of the lecture material provides

a large increase. While the complete version of the mini-course is expected to enhance the awareness of topic with a limited prior knowledge, this is not expected for topics whereof the participants have a large prior awareness.

The results of the in-depth analysis of the learning goals are mainly a tool to further optimize the lecture material. For participants in non-technical training, technical training and technical retraining, quite some variation was seen between the learning goals. With some learning goals having an indication frequency, i.e. how often a learning goal was indicated by the participants, in line with the expectations, while other learning goals were identified (much) more or (much) less than expected. For participants in non-technical retraining, the variation between learning goals was lower, but also the overall frequency of indication was lower. Mainly the learning goals that resulted in a lower indication frequency than expected should be considered in the optimization phase.

Based on the detailed written feedback of the participants, some points of improvement were identified, as can be found in the corresponding reports (see appendix A1-A4). Moreover, some self-assessment questions were added to the mini-course as a proof of concept of a self-assessment tool. With this assessment tool, the stakeholders can test their comprehension after watching the mini-course. Rather than providing a summative evaluation, this self-assessment is aimed at implementing a formative evaluation where the participants get an idea of which topics were understood correctly and where more in-depth information is needed to expand their knowledge base on in silico medicine and in silico trials.

4.2. Phase II

Previously, curricula for technical and non-technical training related to in silico trials in medicine have been proposed (Vander Linden et al., 2023b). The courses that are missing in the current curricula have been identified, together with their corresponding targeted ILOs, based on the analysis of Vander Linden et al. (2023). By using this as a starting point, a syllabus was developed with detailed guidelines on both the organizational aspects and the content (see appendix B1-B4). Related to the organizational aspects, the syllabus contains an overview on the amount and duration of the frontal lectures and practical sessions and how these can be scheduled in a semester of the academic year. With respect to the content, learning goals have been defined, for the frontal lecture as well as the practical session, in correspondence to the targeted ILOs. For the practical session in particular, a general description was added on the type of exercises the students would benefit from. The learning goals and general description indicate the relevant aspects that the students should grasp from the lecture in order to obtain the targeted ILOs after following this course. Nevertheless, there is still room for the authenticity of the instructor. Indeed, instructors can still format the lecture in such a way that it fits with their own background, expertise, lecturing style and the full curriculum at their institution. Instructors are, in this respect, also encouraged to put their own emphases during the course and discuss with colleagues on the applicable notations and the prior knowledge of the students. This authenticity is an essential aspect with the perspective to include these master courses in on-campus curricula. The combination of providing guidelines and therefore a structured and informative starting point, without providing too much restrictions, is expected to increase the motivation of the instructors and, therefore, also of their students.

4.3. Availability of learning material

Following decision of the ISW consortium, the learning material is made available on the electronic learning platform of KU Leuven. To gain access to it, a simple email request needs to be sent to Mr. Peter Stassen, local administrator of this platform. Peter.Stassen@kuleuven.be

5. Recommendations

While first steps have been taken to develop lecture material to (re)train both technical and non-technical groups and the foundation has been set to implement the content in master courses on an institutional level, a continuous effort to realize this training is unavoidable.

5.1. Phase I

For non-technical stakeholders in training and retraining and technical stakeholders in retraining a rather consistent increased awareness was found after following the mini-course. Although the background of these stakeholder groups seems very different, it is not that surprising that the same trend was observed after following their respective mini-course. Indeed, their background is either related to the medical field or to in silico modeling, but the mini-course is one of the first steps that they take in combining both disciplines. This promising result suggests that a mini-course is a good first step to bring these stakeholders in contact with in silico medicine and in silico trials. Ideally, this first mini-course is only a first step. Afterwards, longer and more specific courses are recommended to continue the (re)training. In particular, for non-technical stakeholders in retraining, the extent of belief in the potential benefits of in silico modeling in medicine was variable. A point of attention here is to discuss these potential benefits more explicitly in the mini-course, as belief in its added value might strengthen the motivation to continue the retraining in this domain. Although most of the participants were convinced on the potential added value of in silico modeling in medicine, it should be noticed that the participants are likely to be biased towards an interest in the topic, as they voluntarily tested out the lecture material. Of course, the aim is to familiarize a broad audience to in silico medicine. While convincing them to participate to the mini-course is a first hurdle, a dedicated session to its envisioned added value might contribute to an increased interest in the topic afterwards.

For technical stakeholders, the impact of the mini-course was very topic-dependent. Seen the fact that they already being trained in a discipline that combines the interest for the medical applications of in silico modeling, this result was expected. On the one hand, for topics with a limited prior awareness, the test version of the lecture material provides already a large increase. This indicates that a small amount of lecture material, as in a mini-course, can already have a quite large effect for this stakeholder group. On the other hand, extensive specialist courses are needed to increase the awareness of topic with a high prior knowledge. Combining in-depth courses with mini-courses on new topics is, therefore, recommended to optimize the training of technically-skilled stakeholders. While mini-courses with general modules might be interesting in the initial stages of their training, or even before the start of the training to orient students, a mini-course in further stages of their training should be oriented towards state-of-the-art novel topics. When providing mini-courses for stakeholders in technical training, it is, consequently, crucial moreover to have a good view on the courses they followed before.

The mini-courses themselves can of course also be further improved, both in terms of content and format. Optimization of the content can be provided based on the in-depth analysis of the learning goals. Indeed, this analysis provides insight into the content that the participants grasp from the lecture material and/or consider to be interesting. On the one hand, knowledge of the participants' interest is important as emphasizing those aspects might help in enhancing their motivation. On the other hand, it is also worthwhile to put special attention to those learning goals that were not often considered as key aspects. An alternative approach of those topics in the lecture material could make the content clearer or could even enhance the interest or further emphasize the importance of this aspect, even though it was not considered as interesting in the current version of the lecture material.

One of the major points of improvement regarding the format is the inclusion of interactivity, which also aligns with providing some topic in an alternative format. This helps stakeholders to focus on the lecture material and to actively construct the knowledge themselves. Currently, the question to formulate three aspects after each lecture is an initial implementation of some interactivity, as it encourages participants to process the content they just listened to. The lecture material on verification, validation and uncertainty quantification (VVUQ) includes a hands-on session as well as concept questions and is, in the current stage, already quite interactive. Nevertheless, the interactivity could be enhanced in multiple ways. One way is to include intermediate questions during the online lectures in more lectures. Besides, a self-assessment at the end of the mini-course is recommended as well. This encourages the participants again to think about the lecture content and allows them to evaluate in a formative manner how well they understood the lecture material and to provide feedback on the aspects they did not understand well. This self-assessment is mainly interesting for stakeholders in retraining, as there is no summative evaluation at the end of the course.

Next to including more interactivity, it is also recommended to differentiate more between participants, depending on their needs. In the current mini-courses, differentiation is included by making a distinction between four stakeholder groups. While this is a good starting point, the prior knowledge is of course strongly participant-dependent, in particular for stakeholders in retraining. Currently, the difference in background is accounted for by a short query of the participant's prior knowledge. Indeed, based on their own indication of their prior knowledge, they are referred to online learning material to refresh or expand their prior knowledge. In the mini-course itself, accounting for the difference in prior knowledge could be included by adding a description to more technical or specialized terms that are not explained in detail in the lecture. This allows the participant to read more information on that term in case that would be needed.

As important as optimizing the mini-courses themselves, is the optimization of the evaluation. Currently the knowledge of the participants is evaluated based on asking three key aspects for each part of the lecture material. While this provides already valuable information in terms of aspects that are perceived as interesting and relevant by the participants, this method is prone to interpretation, which makes it difficult to draw objective conclusions. In particular, for participant groups where the available time is considered as very limited, e.g. for non-technical participant in retraining, this might impact the evaluation. Providing limited (less than three) or short key aspects makes it harder to correctly interpret what the participant exactly meant and, thus, link the key aspect to a proper learning goal. Adapting the evaluation format to multiple choice questions could help to assess the impact of the lecture material in a more objective manner. Moreover, this format allows the efficient assessment of all learning goals, instead of a selection of key aspects, and, therefore, does not only provide information to the lecture developers, but also to the participant her/himself. Indeed, the result of the assessment provides the participant with an idea of how well she/he captured the different concepts. In order to retain the information on the interest of participants in particular topics, the participant could be asked to indicate the three learning goals are found to be the most relevant ones. This adapted evaluation format is in particular recommended for the participant groups in retraining, where time is more often considered as an issue, and participants are less likely to follow additional in-depth courses afterwards.

5.2. Phase II

Courses that are required to train the future workforce on in silico trials in medicine well, but that are missing in the current curricula, have been identified. For these courses, syllabi have been developed for the technical and non-technical training stakeholders. The syllabi contain guidelines on the number of frontal lectures and exercise sessions, on the schedule of the lecture, the intended learning goals and the learning goals that should be achieved in each lecture. These guidelines provide a starting point for the instructors of these new courses that should contribute to setting up a qualitative course that effectively fills the gaps in the current curricula. While leaving room for the authenticity of the instructor and coherence with specific curricula in different universities, they give some uniformity to the training of the future workforce on in silico trails as well. These

initial guidelines should, however, be considered as a living document that can be adapted over time, based on the experience of the instructors of these courses. In order to sustain these uniformity, it is recommended to make major adaptation in consultation with other instructors of the same course. An annual meeting on the suggested adaptation in the learning goals could, therefore, be a good strategy to keep on paying attention to the inter-university uniformity.

5.3. Outlook

One of the most important aspects is the enhancement of the dissemination of the developed material. The development of the educational resources has been brought to the attention in the framework of the In Silico World project and is published on Zenodo. It is a challenge to provide further continuation of the material after the end of the project, in terms of optimization, maintenance as well as dissemination.

A mini-course is a good starting point to capture the interest of stakeholders in retraining as time is often a larger hurdle for them. A mini-course might provide an initial idea on some relevant topics for them, while limiting the required time investment. On a personal basis, more in-depth courses can be followed on the most relevant topics.

Also for non-technical stakeholders in training, a mini-course might help the students to orient themselves in the topic, whereafter they can go more into detail on the aspects that are essential for their training. The broader mini-course might provide them, however, with a view on the scope and possibilities of the in silico medicine and in silico trails.

For technical stakeholders in training, the developed mini-course is rather considered as a temporary step in the development process of the lecture material. Indeed, for students interested in in silico modeling and in silico trials elaborate courses are required in a coherent curriculum. For the implementation of such a curriculum, the lacking courses and the corresponding guidelines of phase II are a recommended starting point. Rather than considering the mini-course as a separate entity, the modules of the mini-course can be integrated in the full courses of phase II. Nevertheless, the mini-course could be potentially used to orient students when going from their bachelor's to their master's. Indeed, this mini-course might provide the students insight into what in silico medicine and in silico trials exactly are and could, therefore, help them in making an informed choice. Moreover, the concept of a mini-course with a focus on new techniques and technologies could still be useful for technical stakeholders in training to make them aware of the state-of-the-art without the need to dedicate a full course to these topics.

6. References

Vander Linden, K., Van Looy, G., Davico, G., Viceconti, M., & Vander Sloten, J. (2023a). A systematic approach to define intended learning outcomes for different stakeholders for In Silico Trials (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8380239>

Vander Linden, K., Van Looy, G., Davico, G., Viceconti, M., & Vander Sloten, J. (2023b). Proposal for curricula to train and retrain different stakeholders on In Silico Trials (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10400657>